

Living Together, Dying Alone?

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Plague Judges Everyone!

Samskara (A rite for a dead man) is a great and an inspiring Kannada novel by Jnanapeetha award winner Late U. R. Anatumurthy. It basically critiques the unjust Brahminical social hierarchical system in the context of an epidemic caused by death of many rats. The story begins with the death of Naranappa, a Brahmin who had married a lower caste woman and had broken the Brahminical way of life by eating meat and drinking alcohol. The questions here are: Can his cremation be done according to the Brahminical rites as he had profaned the purity of Brahmins? Can the Dalits enter Brahmin houses to perform the last rites? Does Brahminism leave him though he had left it? Till the last rites are performed Brahmins cannot consume food. As this issue remained unsettled for a long time the epidemic arose and people began to die. The outbreak of disease gave an impartial judgement of death to everyone by putting an end to all kinds of divisions and discriminations based on caste and colour. When human life, existence and survival confronts with caste, division, communalism, partiality etc. the latter loses its battle. The story tells us that Plague judges everyone.

Everyone has Plague!

The 20th-century French existential philosopher Albert Camus's widely read novel *The Plague* (*La Peste*) is relevant today from the context of COVID-19. The key idea of his philosophy is 'life is

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absurd and death renders it meaningless.' A large number of people die in the city of Oran in Algeria due to Plague.

Administration becomes both blind and deaf to the reality and people live in

crisis and disaster. A parish priest preaches people that it is a punishment from God for human sins. Dr. Rieux treats all the affected people, including the priest who had an unrelated illness. The novel reveals the value of love, sacrifice, goodwill and friendship. It shows the absurd, vulnerable and precarious condition of human beings. Camus writes, "Everybody knows that pestilences have a way of recurring in the world; ... There have been as many plagues as wars in history; yet always plagues and wars take people equally by surprise." Camus expresses in the novel that 'everyone has inside it himself this plague, because no one in the world, no one, can ever be immune.' The story mirrors the plight of humans with death as an individual act and community event from which there is no escape. It also metaphorically speaks about the time of World War II, the divisive ideologies, the role of religion, mechanized life, the authoritarianism and silence of responsible leaders. Thus, 'plague' affects everyone.

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Distancing the Distance of Doubt!

John Donne, the 17th-century English poet wrote: "No man is an island, entire of itself, every man is a piece of the continent, a part of the main, ... Any man's death diminishes me, because I'm involved in mankind. And therefore, never send to know for whom the bell tolls; it tolls for thee." The deadly pandemic

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COVID-19 had made not only humanity but also human themselves ‘an island.’ The government administration has asked us to distance ourselves from each other through a lockdown and even we have distanced ourselves from others both for good and bad. The trust and belief with others to welcome, accept, reach out and accommodate others was not possible due to great fear, panic and anxiety of the nature of the disease. The positive side of distancing is to cut the transmission chain of the virus.

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There have been many incidents where people have distanced themselves even in the cases of emergency. For instance, a 41-year-old man from Managluru died in Kodagu in an unfortunate way. He collapsed in the bathroom while bathing. His mother cried for the help from the neighbours but no one came forward out of the fear of coronavirus (NewsKarnataka. 2020). If this is one harsh side of the reality there is also another side, viz. Covid-19 has made all of us to live together as families. It has enabled us to engage ourselves with our parents and siblings and spend quality time with them. In this context, we need to reflect more on inter-relatedness and inter-dependence of human life, existence and death.

Empirical and Existential Insights

Empirically human beings are social by nature. Coming together and living together is fundamental to a human existence fulfilled through family and society. There is mutual dependence in any human institution, whether it is social or political in nature. Scientifically we are made up of cells, molecules and atoms which are inter-connected. In death, our material body becomes one with

the material universe. A metaphysical understanding of human beings as related to one another is meaningfully explained by existential philosophers like Gabriel Marcel, Martin Buber etc. We shall reflect on the reality of life and death, along with them.

Being is Belonging

Gabriel Marcel states that we live in a community. For him, being is belonging. ‘I am not an individual, but I am a whole being having a rapport with the other.’ The ‘other’ constitutes the essence of my ‘self.’ Existence is co-existence and being present for the other. He says that we are living in a ‘broken world.’ Humans are alienated from each other due to mechanization, artificiality and objectification of relationships. Hence, he proposes a relationship of dialogue coupled with availability and freedom.

To Be is to be with

Intersubjectivity is the key idea of Martin Buber. He upholds, “to be is to be with the other.” The human person is essentially a relation and is called to live in relationship. Being together is intrinsic to human existence. Dialogue is the very essence of human life. Dialogue cannot be realized without my communication with the other. He points out two kinds of relationships, i.e., and ‘I-it’ and ‘I-Thou.’ ‘I-it’ is a relationship between subject and object wherein the other is objectified or commodified, whereas ‘I-Thou’ is a relationship between subject and subject. ‘I-Thou,’ presupposes mutuality, acceptance and reciprocity.

To Be is to Die

Human beings live together and co-existence constitutes the core of human living. The next questions in this line that pops up are: If human beings live together, do they die together? Can a person die alone? The philosophy of Martin Heidegger provides rich insights on this issue. Heidegger says that *Dasein* (being) is always 'being-with' and is a 'being-for-death' or 'being-towards-death.' Human being by nature and essence is with others but destined for death. As soon as *Dasein* comes to life, it marches towards the possibility of death. The ultimate end is 'already present' but 'not yet' realized. We can summarize Heidegger's thought on death as 'to be is to die.'

Death is an individual act. It is the most authentic, unique and personal moment of one's life. We can never experience death. One cannot substitute death. In death, one cannot choose, cheat, distract, disown or escape. There is no camouflage in death because it brings authenticity to my existence. I shall be isolated from all things. At the moment of death, others can say, "we are with you," but finally 'I have to die.' I have to face death alone. Death puts me in direct contact with myself.

Is Dying Alone?

Physically a person dies alone. Even from a social or psychological perspective death is an individual act. There is separation from everyone and isolation from everything. Even when one is surrounded by others, one has to die alone. But is he alone metaphysically? It is a complex question without a final and absolute answer.

As a Christian philosopher, I assert that we are a community of the faithful. We are One Holy Catholic Pilgrim Church bound together in joys and sorrows. The final test of our faith is judged on the basis of our reaching out, sharing and caring for others. It is true that a

"Earth has no sorrow that heaven cannot heal." Thomas Moore

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person dies alone. But we, as believers and followers of Jesus Christ, believe that he is not alone. On the Cross, at the time of death, the helpless cry of Jesus was, "My God, My God, why have you forsaken me?" (Matthew 27:46). But the purpose of his life and death was to manifest the truth of "Immanuel," i.e., "God is with us." Christian faith is that even when it seems like the world is falling apart, God is still in control. St. Thomas Moore believes, "Earth has no sorrow that heaven cannot heal."

God says in the Old Testament: "I shall ransom them from the power of Sheol; I shall redeem them from death. O death, where are your plagues? O Sheol, where is your sting? Compassion is hidden from my eyes" (Hosea 13:14). In the context of Covid-19, the suffering person feels the absence of the 'Absolute Reality' which has to liberate him or her. The situation in today's world has reached almost to 'living alone' and 'dying together.'

Why did God harden the heart of Pharaoh which brought about disaster to Israelites? Scripture reveals that God sent ten plagues as a consequence of disobedience and idolatry. They had to bear those plagues in Egypt as 'signs and marvels' of Yahweh. It was a part of God's judgement against sin and his plan to manifest love and mercy. At the end, the people of Yahweh experienced liberation from the slavery in Egypt i.e., God is with them (Exodus, chaps.7-11).

It is said, "Doctor binds the wound and God heals it." We continue to believe in the God-given wisdom to the medical fraternity, i.e., nurses, doctors, scientists etc. Today we all

require each other more than anything. Our relationships need to transcend the world of things, machines and objects. The 'other' is irreducible and inevitable to me. The 'other' is not a burden but a gift and opportunity to me to assert the depth of my own 'self.' Let us make Covid-19 +ve, a negative virus and spread co-existence as a 'positive reality' for we don't live or die alone, rather we live and die together.

Reference

NewsKarnataka. March 31, 2020. "Mangaluru Man Dies in Somwarpet as Corona Scare Keeps Help at Bay." *NewsKarnataka*. Accessed April 7, 2020. <https://www.newskarnataka.com/madikeri/mangaluru-man-dies-in-somwarpet-as-corona-scare-keeps-help-at-bay>.